

APPROACHES IN COMPUTER LINGUADIDACTICS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES USING NETWORK TECHNOLOGIES

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Summary

The thesis is about approaches in computer linguadidactics in teaching foreign languages using network technologies.

Key words

Linguadidactics, systematization, intensification, multimedia, technology, memorization

The use of multimedia presentations in classes are effective for providing visual support for speech learning. The advantages of multi-family presentations include the following:

- combination of text, audio and video visibility;
- possibility of use for interactive presentation;
- multimedia board, which allows you to more clearly semanticize the new lexical, grammatical;
- phonetic material, as well as provide support for training in all types of speech activities;
- ability to use individual slides as a handout (supports, tables, charts, graphs, diagrams);
- intensification of students' attention;
- ensuring the efficiency of perception and memorization of the new educational material;
- control over the acquisition of new knowledge and systematization of the studied material;
- saving training time;
- forming of computer multimedia competence of students.

The use of power point presentations in the educational process simplify the use of various types of language and speech exercises: imitative, substitution, transformational, reproductive.

On the Internet has the opportunity independently create a course with educational materials that would fully meet the set goals and objectives of training. There are specially designed training electronic platforms, aimed directly at educators who would like to create an online course for students.

According to the explanation of the creators of the system, Shoose is "a software product that allows you to create courses and websites based on the

Internet." The main advantage of the course is that is used when creating the course is stored on a general university server, which makes it easy to move, download, while any change automatically becomes visible to the participants of the course.

Using Moodle makes it to solve the problem of integrating various forms of educational activity into a single space where the teacher could control the student's performance of different types of activities, evaluate his work, and most importantly individual students, entire groups and the teacher could work together. The system supports the exchange of files of any format - between the teachers and the students themselves. The distribution service allows you to promptly inform all participants of the course or individual groups about current events.

The technology of forums makes it to organize a training discussion of problems, while the discussion can be carried out both by software groups and with all participants of the course. You can attach files of any format to messages in the forum. The system is equipped with the function of evaluating messages - both teachers and students. Chat allows you to organize an educational discussion of problems in real time. Messaging, comment services are designed for individual communication between a teacher and a student, which may involve reviewing works, discussing individual educational problems. Thus, the use of the Moodle system helps to increase the time and intensity of communication during the training of the foreign language.

For a more complete understanding of the current possibilities of the development of the interactive method of training. Let's consider further the technologies of the new generation of Web-2.0, which are social services for ensuring user communication.

Didactically, the Internet contains two main components: forms of telecommunications and information resources. To the most common forms of telecommunications that is communication via Internet technologies, includes e-mail, chat, forum, ICQ, video, web conferences and others. Forms of television communication also include recently appeared but already quite popular social services Web 2.0, such as blogs, wiki pages, podcast servers and bookmarks, Flickr photo server, YouTube video server and others.

To date, the most common computer technologies that are used in teaching a foreign language are:

- use of internet sites in teaching a foreign language;
- use of skype in teaching a foreign language;

- search by students for additional information on the Internet, software for the teacher's task;

-search for additional information by the teacher on the internet for use in classes on foreign language;

-use of blogs in independent study of a foreign language.

Internet sites help solve a number of didactic problems. For example, Internet sites contribute to the formation of skills and reading skills, using materials from the global Internet; replenishment of vocabulary; formation of motivation to learn a foreign language; expanding the horizons of students, which is the implementation of the process of formation of socio-cultural competence. The successful organization of the sociocultural work of students implies taking into account these factors. At the same time, the independent work of a student is understood as work, for the organization of which the student himself is responsible, who is driven by his internal cognitive motives; which is carried out at the most convenient time for the student.

It is also necessary to note the section of the site, which is very popular among students. This is a video course about English idioms. A video course called the teacher introduces those who learn modern English to the most frequently used idiomatic expressions, about which a professional British actor.

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